

20. **SPRAYING DRONES FOR VINEYARDS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF AGROECOLOGY: RESULTS FROM THE D4AGECOL WORKSHOP IN GREECE**

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ABSTRACT

Over-reliance on high-input, mechanized farming is driving climate change, biodiversity loss, land degradation, and rural inequality. Agroecology offers a holistic alternative by addressing these challenges together. Spraying drones are emerging as labor-saving tools that can reduce drift and soil compaction, but their alignment with agroecological principles and adoption prospects are still unclear. The Digitalisation for Agroecology (D4AgEcol) project aims to evaluate such technologies. This study focused on spraying drones in vineyards, using the FAO's Ten Elements of Agroecology and the ADOPT tool to assess their contribution and adoption potential. A 2024 workshop at the Agricultural University of Athens engaged 27 participants in this dual assessment. Efficiency was rated highest, with scores of 3.75 (local) and 4.00 (EU-wide), driven by perceived cost savings and quality improvements. ADOPT results showed a 19-year path to near-peak adoption, with an estimated peak at 42% and 8.5 years to reach half of that. Spraying drones show promise for agroecology, but realizing their potential will require better training, risk management, and standardized protocols.

Keywords: agroecology, spraying drones, adoption, 10 elements of agroecology, workshop results, D4AgEcol

ΨΕΚΑΣΤΙΚΑ DRONES ΓΙΑ ΑΜΠΕΛΩΝΕΣ ΑΠΟ ΤΗΝ ΠΡΟΟΠΤΙΚΗ ΤΗΣ ΑΓΡΟΟΙΚΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ: ΑΠΟΤΕΛΕΣΜΑΤΑ ΑΠΟ ΤΟ ΕΡΓΑΣΤΗΡΙΟ ΤΟΥ ΕΡΓΟΥ D4AGECOL ΣΤΗΝ ΕΛΛΑΔΑ

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Περίληψη

Η υπερβολική εξάρτηση από εντατικές, μηχανοποιημένες γεωργικές πρακτικές εντείνει την κλιματική αλλαγή, την απώλεια βιοποικιλότητας, την υποβάθμιση των εδαφών και τις κοινωνικές ανισότητες στην ύπαιθρο. Η αγροοικολογία προτείνεται ως μια ολιστική προσέγγιση που αντιμετωπίζει όλα αυτά τα προβλήματα ταυτόχρονα. Τα ψεκαστικά drones κερδίζουν έδαφος ως εργαλεία εξοικονόμησης εργασίας που μειώνουν την παρέκκλιση των ψεκασμών και τη συμπίεση του εδάφους, αλλά η συμβατότητά τους με τις αρχές της αγροοικολογίας και οι προοπτικές υιοθέτησής τους παραμένουν ασαφείς. Το έργο "Ψηφιοποίηση για την Αγροοικολογία" (D4AgEcol) στοχεύει στην αξιολόγηση τέτοιων τεχνολογιών. Η παρούσα μελέτη επικεντρώθηκε στα ψεκαστικά drones σε αμπελώνες, χρησιμοποιώντας τα Δέκα Στοιχεία της Αγροοικολογίας του FAO και το εργαλείο ADOPT για την αξιολόγηση της συνεισφοράς και του δυναμικού υιοθέτησής τους. Ένα εργαστήριο πραγματοποιήθηκε το 2024 στο Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών με τη συμμετοχή 27 ατόμων. Η αποδοτικότητα αξιολογήθηκε ως το σημαντικότερο πλεονέκτημα, με βαθμολογίες 3,75 (σε τοπικό επίπεδο) και 4,00 (σε ευρωπαϊκό), λόγω της μείωσης του κόστους και της βελτίωσης της ποιότητας. Σύμφωνα με τα αποτελέσματα του ADOPT, ο χρόνος για την επίτευξη σχεδόν της μέγιστης υιοθέτησης υπολογίστηκε σε 19 έτη, με μέγιστο ποσοστό υιοθέτησης 42% και 8,5 έτη για την επίτευξη του 50% αυτού. Τα ψεκαστικά drones παρουσιάζουν σημαντικές δυνατότητες για την αγροοικολογία, αλλά η πλήρης αξιοποίησή τους απαιτεί ενίσχυση της κατάρτισης, στρατηγικές διαχείρισης κινδύνου και καθιέρωση πρότυπων πρωτοκόλλων και σκευασμάτων.

Λέξεις κλειδιά: αγροοικολογία, ψεκαστικά ΣΜηΕΑ, 10 στοιχεία αγροοικολογίας, αποτελέσματα διαδραστικού εργαστηρίου, D4AgEcol

1. INTRODUCTION

Agroecology is an integrative approach to sustainable agricultural systems, focusing on the dynamics between biophysical and socioeconomic processes. Its importance lies in delivering sustainable food production, enhancing biodiversity, recycling nutrients, improving soil fertility, and supporting livelihoods for billions of people, particularly smallholder farmers (Ewert et al., 2023). However, the complexity of interactions in agroecological systems demands comprehensive management strategies.

Digital tools, such as terrestrial robots, UAVs, Farm Management Information Systems, IoT systems, and multispectral cameras, have revolutionized agriculture by enabling real-time data collection and decision-making. These systems have significantly enhanced crop production efficiency by improving monitoring and targeting of inputs (Balafoutis et al., 2017; Burns et al., 2022; Anastasiou et al., 2023). Thus, the use of digital technologies in agriculture and specifically in vineyards is critical for enabling agroecology. They offer the data and models required to guide sustainable practice and policy, create resilience in food systems, and, ultimately, contribute to the health of the world and its inhabitants. By using the potential of digital technologies, agroecology may grow to tackle the global issues of food security, environmental sustainability, and climate adaptation (Burns et al., 2022).

Nowadays, the use of UAVs for pest and fertilizer spraying is growing rapidly globally (García-Munguía et al., 2024). According to Maritan et al. (2025), UAV spraying can save €278- 377 ha⁻¹ on flat vineyards and €367-538 ha⁻¹ on steep-slope vineyards depending

on disease pressure, but the high costs of custom-hiring UAVs in Greece make it less profitable, except in situations of extreme labor scarcity and high disease pressure. Gaadhe et al. (2025) concluded that a drone spraying system outperformed a knapsack system in terms of application rate and effective field capacity, with an average application rate of 26.96 l/ha and effective field capacity of 4 ha/h, compared to the knapsack system's 490.28 l/ha and 0.082 ha/h, respectively, under average wind conditions.

Although many studies like the aforementioned have indicated clear benefits of the use of spraying drones for the environment and the economy, farmers are reluctant on adopting them. The reasons may vary and do not depend solely on farmer characteristics but also on the food systems and structures in which farmers operate, as well as the interactions with other value chain actors (Gemtou et al., 2024).

Thus, the main aim of the study was to evaluate the use of spraying drones for vineyards, through the lens of the FAO's Ten Elements of Agroecology and identify the main drivers and barriers that will shape their uptake in European farming systems.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Workshop location and time

A workshop was conducted in 4 April 2024 at the premises of Agricultural University of Athens. In total, 27 stakeholders from academia, research, agriculture and policy making participated in the workshop. The audience was split into two groups to participate in the adoption rate and the agroecological assessments, respectively lasting one hour each.

2.2 ADOPT model assessment

Figure 1. The topics of the 22 questions of the ADOPT model

The ADOPT model created by CSIRO was used for assessment of adoption rate of spraying drones for vineyards. ADOPT is a predictive quantitative model designed to assess the adoption of innovations in agricultural and natural resource management systems (Kuehne et al., 2017). ADOPT stands for 'Adoption and Diffusion Outcome Prediction Tool'. This model and software application help academics, extension workers,

and policymakers understand the variables influencing the adoption of agricultural innovations, practices, and technology. The model is simple and combines several factors, including variables relating to economics, risk, environmental effects, farmer networks, farm and farmer characteristics, as well as the simplicity and comfort of applying new techniques. The model consists of a set of 22 questions which are used for assessing the time to peak adoption and adoption peak level (Figure 1).

For the purposes of the workshop, an individual account was purchased by the corresponding website (<https://adopt.csiro.au/>). The web app has the ability to calculate the adoption peak level and time to peak adoption level automatically and provide the results through a detailed report.

2.3 Agroecological Assessment

The agroecological assessment of spraying drones for vineyards was structured into two main stages, combining both creative exploration and evaluative thinking according to Rustler (2018). Initially, participants engaged in a modified world café approach (The World Café Community Foundation, 2023), discussing a predefined set of indicators related to the FAO’s 10 elements of agroecology. This process involved small groups rotating between tables, remaining consistent to foster deeper exchanges and knowledge sharing (Baumann & Gordalla, 2020). Using structured indicator sheets (Döring et al., 2016), participants highlighted potential positive and negative impacts of spraying drones (Figure 2).

Element of agroecology	Indicator
Diversity	Habitat and landscape diversity
	Crop, tree and livestock diversity on the farm
Co-creation and sharing of knowledge	Diversity of activities, products and services
	Access to data collected by the technology
	Connections among farmers or between farmers and other stakeholders
Synergies	Participation of farmers or other end-users in the development of the technology
	Compatibility with other digital and non-digital technologies
Efficiency	Compatibility with polyculture fields or non-crop plants
	Habitat and landscape connectivity
Recycling	Farm profitability
	Pesticide use
Resilience	Fertiliser use
	Reusability and reparability of the technology
Human and social values	Water saving or recycling
	Reduction or recycling of waste
	Protection against extreme weather events
Culture and food traditions	Protection of farmers against income fluctuations
	Protection against pest and disease attacks
Circular and solidarity economy	Working conditions and wages
	Young people's empowerment and involvement in agriculture
Responsible governance	Data ownership
	Compatibility with local varieties and breeds
Infrastructure readiness	Preservation of farmers' knowledge, skills and identity
	Integration of local culture into the technology
Supporting of policymaking and regulation by data provision	Connecting producers and consumers via local markets and short value chains
	Consumer benefits and fair prices
Sufficiency of risk-assessment related to the use of the technology	Shareability of the technology with other farmers
	Infrastructure readiness

(a)

[Element of agroecology]		Positive effects	Negative effects	Other comments
[Indicator 1]				
[Indicator 2]				
[Indicator 3]				

(b)

Figure 2. (a) The assessed indicators per element of agroecology; and (b) A3 template sheet for the assessment of the selected indicators per element

Following this, participants completed an evaluative survey to rate the overall impacts of the technology on each agroecological element, assess their confidence in these evaluations, and indicate whether their assessments could be generalized from regional to broader European contexts, given that the impacts of digital technologies on agroecology are often context-specific (Finger, 2023) (Figure 3). Finally, targeted discussions deepened insights into the most positively and negatively affected agroecological elements, identifying areas for improvement and potential research priorities.

1. What is the likely overall impact of [name of technology] on [element of agroecology] in [region]?

Not sure | Strongly negative | Strongly positive

0 1 2 3 4 5

2. How confident are you in your answer above?

Not confident at all | Highly confident

1 2 3 4 5

3. The overall impact of [name of technology] on [element of agroecology] that I indicated above also applies to other European regions.

Not sure | Fully disagree | Fully agree

0 1 2 3 4 5

Figure 3. Template of the evaluative survey per element.

3. RESULTS

3.1 ADOPT

Figure 4. Results of the ADOPT model assessment on the adoption rate of spraying drones for vineyards as provided by the report feature of the web platform.

As presented in Figure 4, the anticipated adoption of spraying drones in Greek vineyards is projected to develop gradually over the coming years. It is expected that it will take

approximately 19 years for the technology to approach its near-peak adoption level. This relatively extended timeframe highlights the cautious and measured pace at which vineyard operators are expected to integrate drone technology into their management practices. At its peak, the adoption level is estimated to reach about 42%. This suggests that less than half of the vineyards in Greece will eventually adopt drone-based spraying technologies, reflecting potential constraints such as cost, regulatory hurdles, technological readiness, and cultural acceptance among vineyard managers. In terms of specific adoption milestones, initial uptake will be modest, with just 7% adoption anticipated within the first five years. However, adoption is projected to accelerate somewhat, reaching approximately 27% within a decade. Furthermore, achieving half of the peak adoption rate—around 21% adoption—is expected within roughly 8.5 years from the introduction of the technology

This suggests a cautious yet consistent increase in adoption rates as vineyard operators gradually recognize and embrace the advantages of drone technology in vineyard management. This can be justified by the fact that although there are promising results, important limitations like lack of standardized testing protocols for assessment (García-Munguía et al., 2024) and variable return on investment due to the different topographic, climate and regional characteristics of each field (Maritan et al., 2025) make farmers reluctant on adopting and investing in spraying drones.

3.2 Agroecological Assessment

As presented in Figure 5a, participants perceived spraying drones to have varying impacts on agroecological elements in Greek vineyards. The highest perceived positive impacts were on "Efficiency" (3.75), "Diversity" (3.57), and "Synergies" (3.50), suggesting that spraying drones could significantly enhance operational efficiency and foster beneficial ecological interactions. In contrast, the lowest score was given to "Recycling" (2.17), indicating limited or negative perceptions about how drones influence material recycling or waste management practices. Other areas like "Circular and solidarity economy" (2.88) and "Culture and food traditions" (2.71) received relatively moderate to low scores, reflecting mixed or uncertain outcomes related to cultural and economic sustainability.

Regarding mean confidence in the impact of spraying drones in Greece, participants showed varying levels of confidence in their assessments. High confidence scores were noted particularly in "Synergies," "Culture and food traditions," and "Circular and solidarity economy" (each rated 4.25), signifying strong confidence in their understanding of how drones affect these elements. "Efficiency" also rated highly at 4.13, highlighting consistent confidence about drones improving operational performance. Lower confidence levels were seen in the assessment of "Co-creation and sharing of knowledge" (3.25) and "Recycling" (3.63), suggesting some uncertainty about drones' impacts or a lack of clear evidence or experience in these areas (Figure 5b).

Participants generally felt their assessments for Greece had good applicability at a broader European level, with "Efficiency" scoring highest (4.00). This suggests broad agreement that the efficiency-related benefits of spraying drones can likely be generalized beyond Greece. "Recycling" and "Circular and solidarity economy" had lower scores (3.29), indicating participants' perception that these elements are more context-dependent and less easily generalizable across different European vineyard systems (Figure 5c).

Figure 5. Results of the evaluative survey of the agroecological assessment on (a) the mean impact of spraying drone in Greece; (b) the mean confidence in the impact of spraying drone in Greece; and (c) the applicability of spraying drones at the European scale.

Regarding the results from the targeted discussion, participants concluded for the element of efficiency that spraying drone technology can enhance agricultural efficiency by reducing costs and improving product quality. Through precise and targeted spraying, drones streamline tasks and optimize resource use. Their potential can be further amplified by robust training programs and effective risk management strategies. However, standardized protocols and compatible formulations are needed to help minimize adoption and application challenges, ensuring smoother integration into farming systems. Accordingly for the element of resilience, the participants highlighted that spraying drones can contribute to farm resilience by protecting crops and stabilizing farmers' incomes. Their ability to predict threats and apply pesticides accurately safeguards yields. However, long-term resilience can be strengthened through sustained research, farmer education, and equitable income planning while to prevent over-reliance, a cautious approach to adoption and diversification of farming strategies is required. Similarly, the participants stated for the human and social values element, that the adoption of spraying drones in agriculture can reduce the physical burden on farmers, while increasing safety, and improving decision-making through data access. This technological integration can make farming more attractive to younger generations and empower producers with greater control. However, for maximizing these benefits legal frameworks and comprehensive training are essential. At the same time, addressing concerns like job displacement and ensuring widespread knowledge sharing will support social acceptance. Finally, for the element of culture and food traditions, it was concluded by the participants that spraying drones can help maintain traditional farming practices and protect local crop varieties by enabling precise and minimal-impact applications. Their use can support sustainable agriculture while allowing for the documentation and preservation of cultural heritage.

Strengthening efforts to protect cultural identity and promoting sustainable methods can boost the aforementioned benefits. Meanwhile, safeguards must be in place to prevent the homogenization of farming systems and the loss of traditional knowledge.

The aforementioned statements can be supported by other relevant studies referring to the increased application efficiency and farm resilience while decreasing labor and helping adopting more sustainable farming practices (OECD, 2021; Calderone et al., 2024; Aliloo et al., 2024; García-Munguía et al., 2024; Maritan et al., 2025).

4. CONCLUSIONS

Spraying drones can contribute significantly to the objectives of agroecology. In this study, the results of the workshop showed that participants rated spraying drones highest for the element of Efficiency for both local impact (3.75 out of 5.00) and applicability to other European regions (4.00 out of 5.00). The main reason was that they demonstrated cost reduction and quality improvement. Moreover, participants concluded that spraying drones can significantly enhance agricultural efficiency by reducing costs and improving quality through targeted applications. They also stated that spraying drones can contribute to the element of Resilience by protecting crops and stabilizing income, though long-term impact depends on continued research and cautious adoption. Regarding the element of Human and Social Values, spraying drones can reduce physical labor, increase safety, and attract younger generations, but require strong legal frameworks and training to ensure inclusive benefits. Additionally, while spraying drones can support cultural preservation by enabling sustainable practices and safeguarding local varieties, measures are needed to avoid the loss of traditional knowledge and farming identities. Regarding the ADOPT model results for adoption of spraying drones by winegrape growers, the time to near-peak adoption level was calculated at 19 years and the peak adoption level at 42%, while the time to 50% of peak adoption was calculated at 8.5 years. Finally, enhanced training programs, risk management strategies, and establishment of standardized protocols and formulations must be addressed to realise the full potential of spraying drones.

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